

DIAGNOSTIC PRINCIPLES FOR PSYCHOCORRECTIVE INTERVENTIONS IN CHILDREN WITH RESIDUAL-ORGANIC NEUROSIS-LIKE DISORDERS

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ABSTRACT: Relevance: The functional state of the central nervous system plays a crucial role in determining the behavior of children with residual-organic disorders presenting neurosis-like symptoms and should guide psychocorrective interventions. Purpose: To investigate the functional characteristics of the central nervous system and their influence on cognitive and behavioral processes in children with neurosis-like residual-organic disorders. Materials and Methods: The study included 78 children aged 8-12 years, divided into three groups based on the severity and type of neurosis-like manifestations: Group I - emotional labile disorders (28 children), Group II – enuresis, encopresis, stereotypical movements (23 children), Group III - behavioral disorders such as nail biting and hair pulling (27 children). Functional indicators were assessed using reaction time tests, attention and memory tasks, and neuropsychological methods. Results: Group I showed low CNS excitability with balanced inhibition and excitation; Group II demonstrated high excitability and inhibition inertia; Group III had high excitability with general instability. All groups exhibited reduced cognitive functions, including memory, attention, and thinking. Differences in reaction time, attention, and stability informed targeted psychocorrective strategies. Conclusion: Psychocorrection in children with residual-organic neurosis-like disorders should be tailored according to CNS functional profiles: Group I requires enhancement of cognitive processes, memory, and stability; Groups II and III need combined cognitive and behavioral interventions, with group work particularly beneficial for improving social adaptation in highly excitable children.

Keywords: central nervous system, neurosis-like disorders, residual-organic pathology, psychocorrection, children.

СТРАТЕГИИ ПСИХОКОРРЕКЦИИ У ДЕТЕЙ С ОСТАТОЧНЫМИ ОРГАНИЧЕСКИМИ НАРУШЕНИЯМИ, ПРОЯВЛЯЮЩИМИСЯ НЕВРОЗОПОДОБНЫМИ ПРИЗНАКАМИ: ДИАГНОСТИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ

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Аннотация: Актуальность: Функциональное состояние центральной нервной системы играет ключевую роль в формировании поведения детей с остаточными органическими нарушениями, проявляющимися признаками, сходными с неврозом, и должно учитываться при разработке психокоррекционных мероприятий. Цель: Изучение функциональных особенностей центральной нервной системы и их влияния на когнитивные и поведенческие процессы у детей с остаточными органическими нарушениями, проявляющимися неврозоподобной симптоматикой. Материалы и методы: В исследовании приняли участие 78 детей в возрасте 8–12 лет, разделённых на три группы по степени выраженности и типу неврозоподобных проявлений: Группа I – эмоционально лабильные расстройства (28 детей), Группа II – энурез, энкопрез, стереотипные движения (23 детей), Группа III – поведенческие нарушения в виде грызения ногтей, выдёргивания волос (27 детей). Функциональные показатели оценивались с помощью тестов на время реакции, заданий на внимание и память, а также нейропсихологических методов. Результаты: У детей Группы I наблюдалась низкая возбудимость ЦНС при сбалансированных процессах возбуждения и торможения; у Группы II – высокая возбудимость и инертность торможения; у Группы III – высокая возбудимость при общей нестабильности функционального состояния. Во всех группах отмечено снижение когнитивных функций, включая память, внимание и мышление. Различия во времени реакции, внимании и устойчивости позволили определить целевые стратегии психокоррекции. Выводы: Психокоррекционная работа с детьми с остаточными органическими нарушениями, проявляющимися неврозоподобной симптоматикой, должна проводиться с учётом функционального профиля ЦНС: для Группы I – развитие когнитивных процессов, памяти и устойчивости; для Групп II и III – комбинированные когнитивные и поведенческие вмешательства, при этом групповая работа особенно эффективна для улучшения социальной адаптации у детей с высокой возбудимостью.

Ключевые слова: центральная нервная система, неврозоподобные расстройства, остаточная органическая патология, психокоррекция, дети.

**NEYROZGA O‘XSHASH BELGILAR KO‘RSATADIGAN QOLDIQ-ORGANIK
BUZILISHLARGA EGA BOLALARDA PSIXOKORREKSIYA STRATEGIYALARINI
ISHLAB CHIQUISHDA DIAGNOSTIK ASOSLAR**

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ANNOTATSIYA: Dolzarbligi: Markaziy nerv tizimining funksional holati neyrozga o'xshash belgilar ko'rsatadigan qoldiq-organik buzilishlarga ega bolalarning xulq-atvorini belgilashda muhim rol o'ynaydi va psixokorreksiya tadbirlarini shakllantirishda asos bo'lishi lozim. Maqsadi: Neyrozga o'xshash qoldiq-organik buzilishlarga ega bolalarda markaziy nerv tizimining funksional xususiyatlarini va ularning kognitiv hamda xulq-atvor jarayonlariga ta'sirini o'rganish. Materiallar va usullar: Tadqiqotga 8-12 yoshdagi 78 nafar bola jalb etildi. Bolalar neyrozga o'xshash belgilarining og'irligi va turiga qarab uch guruhga ajratildi: I guruh – emotsional labil buzilishlar (28 nafar bola), II guruh – enurez, enkoprez, stereotipik harakatlar (23 nafar bola), III guruh – tirnoq tishlash, soch tortish kabi xulq buzilishlari (27 nafar bola). Funksional ko'rsatkichlar reaksiya vaqti testlari, diqqat va xotira vazifalari hamda neyropsixologik usullar yordamida baholandi. Natijalar: I guruhda markaziy nerv tizimining past eksitabiligi va muvozanatli inhibitsiya-ekzitatsiya jarayonlari kuzatildi; II guruhda yuqori eksitabiliklik va inhibitsiya inertligi; III guruhda esa yuqori eksitabiliklik va umumiy barqarorlikning yetishmasligi qayd etildi. Barcha guruhlarda kognitiv funksiyalar – xotira, diqqat va fikrlash – pasaygan. Reaksiya vaqti, diqqat va barqarorlikdagi farqlar psixokorreksiya strategiyalarini individuallashtirishga imkon berdi. Xulosa: Qoldiq-organik neyrozga o'xshash buzilishlarga ega bolalarda psixokorreksiya markaziy nerv tizimi funksional profillariga moslashtirilishi lozim: I guruhda kognitiv jarayonlar, xotira va barqarorlikni rivojlantirishga e'tibor qaratish; II va III guruhlarda esa kognitiv va xulq-atvor tadbirlarini birlashtirish zarur, III guruh bolalarida esa guruh ishlari ijtimoiy moslashuvni yaxshilashda muhim hisoblanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: markaziy nerv tizimi, neyrozga o'xshash buzilishlar, qoldiq-organik patologiya, psixokorreksiya, bolalar.

Introduction. The physiological, psychophysiological, and psychological features of the central nervous system largely determine an athlete's individual typological profile and guide behavioral strategies in specific sports [1]. Increasing demands on the athlete, including higher intensity, complexity, and volume of motor activity, require optimal functional readiness of the central nervous system. A key challenge in modern sports physiology is the identification of objective markers to assess CNS functionality [2]. The efficiency of information perception, speed of processing, accurate estimation of spatial-temporal parameters, robust and balanced neural processes, and strong operational memory significantly influence both the choice of sports specialization and the effectiveness of athletic

performance [3]. Autochronometry has a critical role in establishing dynamic physiological stereotypes across bodily functions [4]. Accurate temporal estimation is essential for tactical decision-making, sensorimotor responses, and maintaining movement rhythm. These temporal abilities also support the coordination between somatic and vegetative functions, enhancing overall sports performance [5-7]. Consequently, investigating the typological features of the nervous system and athletes' capacity to estimate different time intervals is essential [8, 9].

Research shows that measuring reaction time is an effective method to evaluate CNS functional status. Objective assessment of cognitive properties can be reliably achieved using neuropsychological and pathopsychological tests [10-13]. In this study, such assessments allowed the identification of potential targets for psychocorrective interventions in children with residual organic disorders presenting neurosis-like symptoms [14-16].

Studies on cognitive brain activity indicate that athletes in fast-paced sports, such as football, demonstrate superior operational and short-term memory compared to non-athletic peers. In contrast, wrestlers often show lower operational memory but higher short-term visual memory [17-20]. These differences reflect sport-specific psychophysiological adaptations: football players must rapidly process large volumes of changing information, make quick decisions, and anticipate opponents' actions, whereas wrestlers rely on rapid situational assessment and immediate motor responses within confined space [21-23].

One of the most informative measures of CNS functional state is the latency of a simple visual-motor reaction (PZMR), which captures fundamental temporal parameters of neural processes critical for psychomotor performance. Assessments based on sensorimotor reactions are widely applied to evaluate adaptation mechanisms in youth from various professional and educational contexts.

The purpose of the study: to determine the features of the functional state of the central nervous system on the basis of indicators of a simple visual-motor reaction in students of medical specialties

Materials and methods. The study sample consisted of 78 children, including 56 boys (72%) aged 8–12 years and 22 girls (28%) aged 8–11 years. Inclusion in the study was limited to children with documented mental retardation, as confirmed by available medical records. All participants received treatment and rehabilitation at the pediatric neuropsychiatric dispensary between 2019 and 2022. Residual effects of organic brain damage were present in all cases.

For diagnostic purposes, participants were stratified into three groups according to the severity and type of neurosis-like symptoms. Group I included 28 children with emotionally labile (asthenic) disorders [F 06.06]. Group II comprised 23 children exhibiting enuresis, encopresis, and stereotypical motor behaviors [F 98.0; F 98.1; F 98.3]. Group III included 27 children presenting behavioral disturbances such as nail biting and hair pulling [F 98.8; F 98.9].

Assessment of the functional state of the central nervous system was conducted using a specialized computer program designed to evaluate reaction time characteristics, including simple sensorimotor responses and reactions to moving stimuli under specific conditions. This program was based on a methodology developed to study neural function and processing.

To examine attention parameters (stability, concentration, and capacity), the Toulouse-Pieron technique and Schulte tables were employed. Short-term auditory-verbal memory was assessed using a ten-word recall task. Reasoning abilities were evaluated through metaphor interpretation tests and tasks requiring the exclusion of redundant words, based on a standard neuropsychological test battery.

The clinical method was also applied, involving direct observation of children's behavior both in experimental settings and during routine activities in a sanatorium-hospital environment. To determine the statistical reliability of observed differences, the non-parametric Mann-Whitney U test was used.

Results and their interpretation. The analysis of simple sensorimotor reaction (SSR) times revealed notable differences across the study groups. Children in Group I exhibited the longest reaction times ($631,32 \pm 54,02$ ms), while Group II demonstrated the shortest reaction times ($478,62 \pm 58,03$ ms), with these differences reaching statistical significance ($u = 199, p \leq 0,05$). Group III showed intermediate values ($494,09 \pm 43,01$ ms), though the differences did not achieve statistical reliability.

Further assessment using the more complex selection reaction task (RV) indicated that children in Group II responded faster ($657,97 \pm 82,19$ ms) than those in Group I ($1185,9 \pm 181,18$ ms), with significant differences confirmed ($p \leq 0,05$). Group III again presented intermediate results ($819,5 \pm 102,56$ ms), without statistically significant differences. In tasks requiring reverse reconstruction, Group I children showed a decrease in reaction time during RV reconstruction ($1303,5 \pm 218,95$ ms with reconstruction vs. $1156,56 \pm 225,66$ ms without reconstruction). In Group II, differences between reorganized and non-reorganized RV times were less pronounced ($703,41 \pm 110,55$ ms vs. $657,82 \pm 82,19$ ms), while in Group III, children showed slightly longer reaction times without reconstruction ($977,75 \pm 157,59$ ms) compared to reconstruction ($969,75 \pm 158,59$ ms).

Evaluation of reaction times to a moving object revealed that Group II had the fastest responses ($49,61 \pm 6,91$ ms), while Group I children had the slowest ($77,36 \pm 8,94$ ms), though this difference was not statistically significant. Differences between Group III ($65,95 \pm 12,07$ ms) and Group I were statistically reliable ($u = 224, p \leq 0,05$).

Attention assessment using the Schulte tables showed a decrease in both volume and concentration across all groups (mean values: Group I – $85,21 \pm 5,18$ s; Group II – $85,65 \pm 10,11$ s; Group III – $79,01 \pm 6,21$ s). The Toulouse-Pieron test demonstrated higher processing rates in Groups II ($37,17 \pm 1,85$ characters/min; $u = 197, p \leq 0,05$) and III ($38,56 \pm 1,81$ characters/min; $p \leq 0,05$) compared to Group I ($31,94 \pm 2,03$ characters/min). Accuracy of task performance was highest in Group II ($3,46 \pm 0,67\%$ errors), while Groups I and III showed similar levels of errors ($5,15 \pm 1,61\%$ and $5,12 \pm 1,13\%$, respectively). This suggests that in Group III, increased task speed may have been achieved at the expense of accuracy. Children with longer reaction times (Group I) generally demonstrated lower attention productivity.

All groups exhibited reduced memory and cognitive performance. Short-term and delayed memory tasks revealed difficulty recalling six or fewer words, while reasoning deficits manifested as impaired interpretation of figurative meanings, difficulty generalizing concepts, focusing on subtle features, reliance on concrete situational thinking, and low verbal experience.

The UR indicator, reflecting reaction stability, emerged as a sensitive predictor of central nervous system (CNS) functional decline due to fatigue. Early CNS activity changes were marked by instability in neural processes, providing a reliable metric for evaluating functional state. Normal reaction stability was observed in 22,73% of boys and 25,49% of girls. Reduced stability was noted in 9,09% of boys and 15,69% of girls, while slightly reduced stability occurred in 65,91% of boys and 58,82% of girls. Deep inhibition or excitation of the CNS, indicated by "limited" reaction stability, was observed in 2% of participants, all boys; no girls displayed this level. Overall, these findings suggest a mild decrease in the functional capacity of executive CNS systems in children across groups.

Functional interhemispheric asymmetry was also examined, reflecting physiological and psychological differences between the cerebral hemispheres. One manifestation, motor asymmetry, was observed in approximately 25% of students, indicating unequal participation of body parts in response to stimuli. Specifically, 20% of boys and 24% of girls exhibited stronger left-hand responses. Environmental factors, such as residence in extreme climatic and geographical conditions, may influence lateral phenotypes, leading to an increased proportion of left-lateralized individuals in certain populations.

In summary, the study demonstrates significant variability in CNS functional indicators among children with residual-organic neurosis-like disorders. Group I was characterized by low CNS excitability with balanced inhibition, Group II exhibited high excitability and inertia of inhibition, and Group III showed high excitability with general instability. These functional profiles have important implications for targeted psychocorrective interventions, highlighting the need to consider individual CNS characteristics in the design of cognitive and behavioral rehabilitation programs.

Conclusions. Analysis of the functional state of the central nervous system (CNS) in the examined groups revealed significant differences. Children in Group I exhibited low CNS excitability with balanced processes of excitation and inhibition. In contrast, Group II participants demonstrated high excitability, inhibition inertia, and an overall imbalance of neural processes. Children in Group III showed markedly high excitability combined with a lack of inhibitory regulation and general instability of CNS functional state.

Despite these differences in CNS dynamics, all groups displayed similar impairments in cognitive processes, including memory, attention, and thinking, with variations between groups being minimal.

The functional state of the CNS plays a determining role in the behavioral characteristics of children with residual-organic neurosis-like disorders, which must be considered when designing psychocorrective interventions. For Group I, where behavioral disturbances are minimal, psychocorrection should focus primarily on enhancing cognitive processes, attention, stability, and memory. For children in Groups II and III, intervention should combine cognitive rehabilitation with behavioral correction, emphasizing the development of self-control skills. In Group III, group-based methods are particularly important, as high excitability presents challenges for social adaptation, largely due to difficulties in acquiring new behavioral patterns.

References:

1. Aleksandrovna K. O. et al. Clinical and psychological characteristics of patients with alcoholism with suicidal behavior //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11. – C. 399-404.
2. Anatolyevna S. Y. et al. Suicide prevention in adolescents with mental disorders //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11. – C. 303-308.
3. Antsiborov S. et al. Association of dopaminergic receptors of peripheral blood lymphocytes with a risk of developing antipsychotic extrapyramidal diseases //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 29-35.
4. Borisova Y. et al. Concomitant mental disorders and social functioning of adults with high-functioning autism/asperger syndrome //Science and innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. D11. – C. 36-41.
5. Habibullayevich S. S. et al. Depression and post-traumatic stress disorder in patients with alcoholism after the covid-19 pandemic //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – T. 2. – №. 11. – C. 420-429.

6. Hazratovich K. Z. et al. The degree of adaptation to psychogenic effects in social life in patients with psychogenic asthma //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 295-302.
7. Holdorovna I. M., Murodullayevich K. R., Temirpulotovich T. B. Problems of consciousness disorder in modern psychiatry //Journal of healthcare and life-science research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 20-27.
8. Ibragimova M., Turayev B., Shernazarov F. Features of the state of mind of students of medical and non-medical specialties //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D10. – С. 179-183.
9. Ivanovich N. A. et al. Alcohol dependence and manifestation of autoaggressive behavior in patients of different types //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 413-419.
10. Lapasovich B. S., Usmanovich O. U., Temirpulotovich T. B. Алкоголизмга чалинган беморларда турли дори воситаларни сунистеъмол қилишининг клиник хусусиятлари //Journal of biomedicine and practice. – 2023. – Т. 8. – №. 4.
11. Murodullayevich K. R., Holdorovna I. M., Temirpulotovich T. B. The effect of exogenous factors on the clinical course of paranoid schizophrenia //Journal of healthcare and life-science research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 28-34.
12. Nikolaevich R. A. et al. Diagnosis of depressive and suicidal spectrum disorders in students of a secondary special education institution //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 309-315.
13. Novikovich A. S. et al. Experience with the use of memantine in the treatment of cognitive disorders //Science and Innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 11. – С. 282-288.
14. Ochilov U. et al. The main forms of aggressive manifestations in the clinic of mental disorders of children and adolescents and factors affecting their occurrence //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 42-48.
15. Rotanov A. et al. Social, socio-cultural and behavioral risk factors for the spread of hiv infection //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 49-55.
16. Sedenkova M. et al. Basic principles of organizing gerontopsychiatric assistance and their advantages //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 63-69.
17. Sedenkova M. et al. Features of primary and secondary cognitive functions characteristic of dementia with delirium //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 56-62.
18. Solovyova Y. et al. Protective-adaptive complexes with codependency //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 70-75.
19. Spirkina M. et al. Integrated approach to correcting neurocognitive defects in schizophrenia //Science and innovation. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. D11. – С. 76-81.
20. Temirpulotovich T. B. Effects of social factors in children with anxiety-phobic disorders //Journal of healthcare and life-science research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 10. – С. 35-41.
21. Temirpulotovich T. B. Somatoform variant post-traumatic stress disorder //Journal of healthcare and life-science research. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 9. – С. 45-52.
22. Turayev B. T., Ochilov U. U., Kubayev R. M. Distribution of anxiety and depression in affective disorders of somatized depression //International medical scientific journal. – 2015. – С. 60.
23. Usmonovich O. U., Temirpulotovich T. B. The influence of the presence of mentally ill children in the family on the psyche of parents //Journal of education, ethics and value. – 2023. – Т. 2. – №. 8. – С. 68-75.